

A CONCEPTUAL STUDY ON RASAYANA CHIKITSA IN AYURVEDA WITH
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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda, is a core element of healthcare delivery systems, emphasizes not only on treating the disease but also maintaining health and preventing illness. Thus, in *Ayurveda* first preference is given for maintenance of health and the prevention of disease. In *Ayurveda*, two primary objectives are outlined for treatment: the first is *Swasthasya Swasthya Rakshanam* (maintaining the health of the healthy person) and the second is *Aturasya Vikara Prashamnama* (to cure the ailments of the diseased person). To achieve these objectives, three types of *dravyas* have been mentioned in *Ayurveda*- *Dosh-prashamaka*, *Dhatu-pradushaka* and *Swasthya-hitkara*. *Swasthyahitkara Dravyas* are the primary element for maintaining health. *Rasayana* is also a crucial factor for the preservation of health. Due to its properties, *Rasayana* has been described as an independent therapy among the *Astanga* (eight parts) disciplines of *Ayurveda*. *Rasayana* therapy, a core concept of *Ayurveda*, plays a significant role in rehabilitation by promoting rejuvenation, enhancing immunity, and restoring balance and vitality after illness or physical trauma. It involves holistic methods aimed at rebuilding and strengthening the *dhatu*s (body's tissues), enhance immunity, and promoting mental and emotional well-being. Thus, *Rasayana* therapy supports comprehensive recovery and long-term health.

KEYWORDS: *Rasayana*, Rehabilitation, *Ayurveda*, *Dosha-prashamaka Dravyas*, *Dhatu-pradushaka Dravyas*, *Swasthyahitkar Dravyas*.**INTRODUCTION**

Despite notable advancements in modern medical science, including sophisticated diagnostic tools and a detailed understanding of human physiology, complete control over diseases remains a challenge, rather than new health challenges are emerging. *Ayurveda* not only address the treatment but also the prevention of diseases by enhancing immunity and strength. It includes a dedicated field known as *Rasayana*, which slows down the ageing process and reduces the severity of illness intensity occurring in old age by rejuvenating Cellular Processes that modulate the body's metabolic processes and immune responses. It is the solution pathway to the problem of healthful longevity. It enhances the micro-circulation and tissue perfusion which leads to the development of nourished, strong and healthy tissues in the body, as a result an individual gains a longer life, enhanced immunity, vitality, happiness and improved

intellectual capacity etc. *Rasayana* drugs are considered to possess as nutritional tonics, antioxidants, anti-stress, adaptogenic and immuno-modulatory effects.

Rasayana can also be disease-specific, by stimulating a specific immune reaction and bio-strength to counteract a specific disease. This principal resonates strongly with the objectives of rehabilitation, which aims to help individuals regain, maintain, or improve their functional abilities, enabling them to lead independent and fulfilling lives. Rehabilitation encompasses various types, including physical therapy, occupational therapy, speech therapy, and cognitive rehabilitation, along with psychological support to address emotional and mental challenges during the recovery process.

Acharya Charaka has described several benefits of *Rasayana*, including the promotion of *Dirgha Ayu*

(longevity), *Smruti* (Memory), *Medha* (Intellect), Health, and Youthfulness. *Rasayana* is described as enhancing *Prabha* (luster), *Vrana* (Complexion), *Svara* (Voice), Strength of the body and functions of both sense and motor organs to their optimum level.^[1] Further Acharya Charaka mentions that *Rasayana* is a promotive of longevity, preservative of youth, removes- sleep, drowsiness, exertion, exhaustion, lassitude and debility, restores equilibrium of *vata-pitta-kapha*, brings stability, alleviates laxity of muscles, stimulative of digestion and metabolism and promotive of luster, complexion and voice. By using *Rasayana* the great sages like *Chyavana Rishi* regained youthful age and became charming for women, they also attained firm, even and well divided muscles, compact and stable physique, blossomed strength, complexion and senses, uninterrupted power and endurance, thereby Acharya Charaka confirmed the properties of *Rasayana*.^[2]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ayurvedic Samhitas and textual materials have been used for this study. Various references have been collected. Modern texts, related websites, and related articles have also been consulted.

Conceptual Study

Etymology of Rasayana

Rasayana is a word of Sanskrit language. The *Rasayana* is combination of two words- “*Rasa*” and “*Ayana*”. *Rasa* means the essence of *Ahara Rasa* or the first *Dhatu* formed in the process of *Dhatu Utpatti Krama*. Here the word *Rasa* denotes appropriate *Dhatu* (*Prashasta Dhatu*) and the word *Ayana* denotes the “passage” (channels of the body, from which *Dhatu*s are transformed and transported from one to another place) or “to gain”. Simply the meaning of *Rasayana* word is to gain the appropriate *Dhatu*s by material or methods.

According to Acharya Dalhan, *Rasayana* is to impose *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Virya*, *Vipak* of a drug to the body, to increase life span and potency and to check the adverse effects of old age by the formation of *Prashasta Dhatu* (appropriate *Dhatu*).^[3]

Definition of Rasayana

भेषजं द्विविधं च तत्

स्वस्थस्योर्जस्करं किञ्चित् किञ्चिदार्तस्य रोगनुत्^[4]

स्वस्थस्योर्जस्करं यत्तु तद्वृष्यं तद्रसायनम्^[5]

According to *Ayurveda*, *Bhesaja* (Therapeutics) is of two types - the one which promotes strength (immunity) in healthy, and the other that alleviates disorders in ailing. Thus, the drugs are of two kinds, one that goes for healthy group and other belongs to the curative group. The group of drugs for healthy group are sub- divided into two types as per quotation i.e. “One is *vrushya* (virilific) and the other is *Rasayana* (vitalizer).

प्रायः, प्रायेण रोगाणां द्वितीयं प्रशमे मतम्

प्रायःशब्दो विशेषार्थो ह्युभयं ह्युभयार्थकृत्^[6]

The word ‘*Prayah*’ (mostly) denotes only particularity because both the group perform both the above functions (promotion of strength including immunity and alleviation of disorders)

लाभोपायो हि शस्तानां रसादीनां रसायनम्^[7]

Rasayana (promotive treatment) means the way for attaining excellent *rasa* etc. (*dhatu*s).

Acharya Sushruta dealing with *Shalya* and *Shalakyata* *Tantra* has not emphasized much on *Rasayana Tantra* as that of *Acharya Charaka*, thereby *Acharya Sushruta* describes *Rasayana* as *Vayasthapana* (the therapy which establishes the age), *Ayuskar* (increases the life span), *Medha*(intelligence) and *Bala* (Strength) as well as it enables the person to rid of the diseases.^[8] The word “*Vayasthpana*” well described by *Acharya Dalhana*, as it promotes longevity by enabling the person to live a full lifespan of 100 years, secondly makes the man to live young for a prolonged duration thus delaying the onset of *Jara* (aging). One observation made by *Acharya Sushruta* is regarding the selection of age of the subject for *Rasayana* therapy i.e., in younger and middle age groups.^[9] He has also given description of various drugs like *Vidange*, *Kashmari*, *Bala*, and the divine drugs like 24 types of *soma*. *Acharya Vagbhata* has followed *Acharya Charaka* in giving the definition of *Rasayana*, and have incorporated many newer drugs of medicinal use such as ‘*Rason*’ (Garlic) and ‘*Palandu*’ (Onion). *Acharya Charaka* has given very much importance to the subject, as the first word of this *Samhita* is “*Dirghjivanam*” (means the long life) and the first chapter is subdivided into four chapters on *Rasayana* therapy, which explores the physiological, pharmacological, therapeutics and clinical perspectives of the subject. Around 200 *Rasayana* drugs, the single and the compound, herbs and the minerals are described there. In *Kashaypa Samhita*, no separate chapter on *Rasayana* is seen but scattered use of *Rasayana* drugs can be seen in this *Samhita*. *Acharya* also suggested *Snehana*, *Swedana* and *Samsodhana karmas* before the *Rasayana* therapy. Special drugs mention in *Samhita* are *Brahmi*, *Lasuna* as single drugs and *Satpuspa* and *Lasuna kalpa*.

Acharya Bhavaprakasha has given an independent chapter of *Rasayana*, where he specially mentions the use of cold water, milk, ghee, *Punarnava Rasayana*, *Ashvagandha Rasayana*, etc. He has not described any classification of *Rasayana*. Some newly introduced yoga by *Acharya Bhavaprakasha* is *Manjishtha*, *Mushali*, *Kumari*, *Shalmali*, *Parad*, *Gandhaka*, *Hartala*, etc. Thus, the practices of *Rasayana* therapy have existed in vedic period but in *Charaka Samhita* the *Rasayana* therapies has been considered as utmost important thereby giving an independent status. Thus, all the *Rasayana therapies*,

Rasayana kalp, *Rasayana drugs*, etc. described in our *Samhitas* emphasizes not on just restoring physical abilities, but also on mental and social wellbeing after disease, injury, or surgery because the therapies described have an holistic effects, addressing not only the bodily aspects but also the emotional and mental after effects of illness or injury, thereby supporting reintegration into daily life with improved quality of life.

Classification of *Rasayana*

Classification of *Rasayana* can be done on various bases. Some of the patterns of classification are enlisted below.

A) Classification based on *Bheshja Bheda*

I. *Sadravya Rasayana*

Application of *Rasayana* by using certain substance /drug

e.g., *Amalaki Rasayana*; *Pippali Rasayana*.

II. *Adravya Rasayana*

Application of *Rasayana* without using any substance /drug

e.g., *Achar Rasayana*.

B) Classification based on purpose of application of *Rasavana*

I. Promotive and Prophylactic *Rasayana*

Application of *Rasayana* to promote positive health, slow down ageing process and disease progression e.g. *Chyavanprash*.^[10]

II. Curative and preventive *Rasavana*

Use of *Rasayana* to treat specific ailments and prevent their recurrence, e.g. *Pippali Rasayan* For disorders of *Pranvaha Srotasa*.^[11]

III. *Medhva Rasavana*^[12]

A separate class of *Rasayana* drugs has been described in the text for specifically enhancing '*Medha*' (Memory, will power, intelligence). e.g., *Mandukpami*, *Yashti madhu*, *Guduchi*, *Shankhapushpi*.

IV. *Achara Rasavana*^[13]

Besides the use of drugs, it has been claimed that similar *Rasayana* effects both in the body as well as on the mind may be achieved by practising an improved code of Socio-behavioral conduct i.e., '*Sadachara*'

C) Classification as per *Dalhana's commentry*

Acharya Dalhana while commenting on 27th chapter in *Chikitsa Sihana* of *Sushruta Samhita* has classified the *Rasayana* under the following main three groups.^[14]

I) *Kamya* II) *Naimittika* III) *Ajasrika*

I) *Kamya Rasayana*: Indicated for healthy person, for preservation and promotion of health and also promote vigour and vitality.

It is further categorized into the following three types

a) *Prana Kamya* – enhance life vitality and longevity, ex- *Triphala Rasayana*, *Haritaki Rasayana*

b) *Medha Kamya* – enhance intellect and mental functions, ex- *Brahmi*, *Shankhpuspi*

c) *Sri Kamya* – enhance immunity, vigour, complexion and lustre, ex- *Amalki Rasayana*, *Loha Rasayana*

II) *Naimittika Rasayana*: Specific *Rasayanas* have been advocated for specific diseases to be used as adjuncts to the general treatment. Such *Rasayana* drugs are known as *Naimittika Rasayana*, e.g. *Shilajatu* for *Madhumeha*.

III) *Ajasrika Rasayana*: *Rasayana* to be used on daily basis or frequently all the time, e.g. *Ghrit*, *Madhu*, *Kshir*. It promotes longevity, intellect, strength and lustre of the body.

D) Classification based on methods of use of *Rasavana*.

The *Rasayana* therapy is practised by two methods.

I. *Kuti-Praveshika* (indoor regimen) considered to be the ideal method of application of *Rasayana*.

II. *Vatatapiaka* (outdoor regimen), considered as practical method of application of *Rasayana*.

I. *Kuti Praveshika Rasayana*

It is the ideal method of application of *Rasayana*, in which the environment and activities are rigidly controlled, and powerful medicines are used to completely reverse the process of ageing and achieve youthfulness. It is also known as the indoor regimen for practising *Rasayana* therapy.

The *Kuti Praveshik* method is recommended for persons who are capable, disease - free, wise, self-controlled leisurely and rich.^[15] This method is very demanding and requires strict discipline regarding diet and activities. It entails prolonged isolation, and the person should be properly informed about the complete plan and mentally prepared for what may initially appear to be an ordeal. As the person adapts to the routine, the physician administers purification treatments to clear the bowels and channels and ensure equilibrium of the *Dosha*.

When the body is ready to respond to medication, the physician prepares the required medicine of requisite potency and store it in a golden or silver or earthen vessel, lined with *ghrita* and properly closed. The medicine is specially prepared to strengthen '*Rasa Dhatu*' which in turn nourishes and strengthen the other *Dhatu*s. Plants from the *Jeevaniya gana* and *Balya gana* are primarily used in the formulation and processed according to the principles described in the classical text.

An appropriate dose of this medication is administered to the person in the late morning on an empty stomach when he is hungry. This ensures quick and complete digestion and absorption. The subject spends most of the time in reading philosophy and practising meditation. The medication is administered daily, and the dosage is adjusted according to the patient's response.

Favourable effects of therapy become obvious in three to six months. When the desired effects are achieved, the dose of the medication is gradually reduced, and the

patient is encouraged to come in the middle portion of the housing and meet friends and relatives under the physician's supervision. Once he gets acclimatized to the middle portion and commences his normal diet, the medication is discontinued and the patient is encouraged to come in the outer portion of the quarters. This should be done gradually. The person can meet his friends and commence his normal activities as he gets acclimatized to the external environment. By this time, the person should be full of vigor and vitality and would have regained youthful appearance. If he lives in a clean and healthy environment eats wholesome and compatible food avoids excesses and indiscretions in behaviour, he will live a long and healthy life without suffering from diseases associated with old age.

II. Vatatapika Rasayana

Patients receive Rasayana therapy as outdoor patients i.e., enabling them to move freely in open air and sunlight, known as *Vata-tapika Rasayana*. Only mild drugs can be given in this type of *Rasayana*.

DISCUSSION

In Ayurveda, maintenance of health and origin of disease is determined by the quality and quantity of food consumed, eating behaviours, lifestyle choices, mental well-being, and environmental factors. Thus, food is a key determinant in the maintenance of health with due consideration of the status of *Agni* (digestion and metabolism mechanics) and suitability assessment in relation to *Prakriti* (body constitution). Considering this fact, healthy and nutritious food habits have been considered as *Ajasrika Rasayana* (includes nourishing healthy food). Thus, awareness about the importance of healthy food and dietary practices among the society must be reintroduced keeping in mind the present lifestyle of the people.

Some *Rasayanas* exhibit disease specificity and are administered in particular disease states, as they prevent specific disease by stimulating that specific immunity and bio-strength, called as *Naimittika Rasayana*, these *Rasayana* drugs can be administered along with the medication of the underlying disease to boost the disease-combating power and immunity so that faster and better relief may be provided and recurrences may be prevented. For example, simple herbs like *Guduchi*, *Amalaki* can be given to person in prediabetes state and thus can prevent diabetes.

Similarly, in diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis or pulmonary tuberculosis, etc. autoimmune disorders adding *Rasayana* drug as supportive medication to ongoing medication can also yield favourable results and thereby improving patients life quality. Moreover, intake of *Medhya Rasayana* has given remarkable results in patients quality of life in neurodegenerative conditions such as Alzheimers disease, senile dementia or in stress induced condition such as anxiety and insomnia. The Four *Medhya Rasayana* mentioned in *Charak Samhita*

are- *Mandukpami* juice, *Yashtimadhu* powder with milk, *Guduchi* (Stem) juice along with its root and flowers and *Shankhapushpi* paste – these are life promoting, disease eradicating, promoters of strength, *agni*, complexion, voice and are intellect promoting. Out of them, *Shankhapushpi* is specifically intellect promoting.

Rasayana having the multi-aspect mode, it can be said that Ayurveda's primary approach centered on evaluation and assessment of health parameters, and its preservation, and thus, Ayurvedic treatment is defined as all interventions- including dietary regulation, lifestyle modifications, or medicines- aimed at achieving the target of *Dhatu Samya* (state of homeostasis) and not only treating the disease.

Rasayana is a broad-spectrum discipline of *Ayurveda*, which includes selective application of medicinal herbs, phyto-mineral formulations, nutritional food products, and lifestyle modifications along with inner-control and adherence to good conduct, it aims to attain the physiological Homeostasis so that there is minimal effect of etiological factors on the body. In other words, *Rasayana* serves as a pathway to attain the optimal state of body tissues and physiological systems.

Rasayana therapy in Ayurveda is focused on rejuvenation, enhancing vitality, slowing aging, and promoting tissue strength and recovery. These effects align with key objectives in rehabilitation science: restoring function, promoting healing, and improving quality of life after disease or injury.

Scientific studies and rehabilitation centers increasingly integrate Ayurvedic therapies, including *Rasayana*, with physical rehabilitation modalities. This integration supports improved outcomes in neurological, musculoskeletal, and post-surgical rehabilitation. For example, Ayurvedic medicine, through *Rasayana* herbs like *Ashwagandha* and *Amalaki*. *Ashwagandha*'s root extract has also been proven effective in patients with osteoarthritis of knee, in relieving pain and in reducing disability^[16] thereby boosting physical resilience, reduce fatigue, support tissue repair, and improve both immunity and functional recovery, which are critical in rehabilitation settings.

Clinical trials suggest supplementation of *Ashwagandha* can facilitate better endurance, energy restoration, and reduction of stress hormones, all contributing to faster and more sustained rehabilitation—especially relevant for patients recovering from injuries or chronic diseases requiring physical therapy.^[17]

The leaf extract of *Amalaki* rapidly exhibits protective effects against lipid peroxidation by scavenging free radicals thereby minimizing the chances of diabetic complications. Evidence from clinical studies suggests that *Amalaki* can be an effective adjunct for enhanced glucose control, reduced complications, and tissue

protection in rehabilitation of diabetic patients or others with metabolic syndromes.^[18] *Amalaki* is regarded as the best medicine for *Vayasthapana*.

Ayurveda-based rehabilitation programs frequently merge *Rasayana* therapy with conventional physiotherapy. Such integrated programs have proven beneficial for improving the range of motion, reducing muscle spasm and stiffness, enhancing circulatory health, and preventing muscle wasting after injuries or surgeries. They are also utilized in neurological rehabilitation, such as for stroke or spinal cord injury, to promote neuronal regeneration and functional independence.

Rasayana therapies can be scientifically connected with rehabilitation by their ability to accelerate recovery, restore function, support tissue healing, and promote overall resilience after disease or injury.

CONCLUSION

In Ayurveda, *Rasayana* therapy serves as a mainstay of rehabilitation by.

- Enhancing cellular repair and tissue regeneration thereby replenishing and strengthening bodily tissues, ensuring their optimal function and balance.
- Enhancing *vyadhikshamatva* (immunity), which is crucial for recovery and prevention of disease recurrence.
- Promoting mental health, improving memory, intelligence, and emotional well-being, which supports holistic recovery.
- Acting as an anti-aging and disease-modifying therapy, it slows down the degeneration caused by chronic conditions or trauma.

Overall, *Rasayana* in Ayurvedic rehabilitation promotes physical endurance, mental resilience, and cellular repair, making it a natural and sustainable modality for restoring health and enhancing quality of life during and after recovery phases.

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